

Historical Shifts in Asylum Policies in Switzerland: Between Humanitarian Values and the Protection of National Identity

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Abstract

As in many other European countries, the issue of asylum seeking has become in Switzerland a central issue of public debate, and immigration and refugee policies have become a top political priority. Pressure to make asylum policies more restrictive has increasingly come from right-wing populist parties that have become stronger over the past decade. This paper examines the shifts in policies and state discourses of refugees in Switzerland from the end of the 19th century up to today. The study is based on the perspective of critical discourse analysis, “an approach that specifically focuses on the role of discourse in the reproduction of power, dominance and inequality” (van Dijk, 2004: 20). The practical study of state discourse focuses on three dimensions of analysis: the discourse itself, the context of discourse, and the historical events surrounding the discourse. The paper shows that the evolution of state representations of refugees in Switzerland has evolved from a predominantly humanitarian attitude towards asylum-seekers before the First World War to a mainly defensive attitude, which partly persists today, where asylum-seekers are increasingly perceived as a cultural threat and a financial burden. It demonstrates that imaginations of race, class and political systems have been main factors in structuring shifting state representations of refugees.

1 Introduction

One of the defining global issues of the early 21st century was the asylum for refugees. Between 1980 and 2004, 9.9 million applications for asylum were lodged in 39 countries in Europe, North America, Oceania and Asia. In 2004, most claims were registered in Europe (444'000), followed by the Americas (84'000), Africa (82'000), Asia and the Pacific (35'000). In Europe, the countries with the largest numbers of applications were France (61'058), the United Kingdom (40'202), Germany (35'613), Austria (24'676), Sweden (23'161), Belgium (15'358) and Switzerland (14'248) (UNHCR, 2005a). The issue of asylum seeking is currently one of the central challenges faced by European states, and immigration and refugee policies have become a top political priority. Pressure to make asylum policies more restrictive has

increasingly come from right-wing populist parties that have emerged in several countries over the past decade. Xenophobic discourses and defensive immigration and refugee policies are at the centre of these parties’ political programmes and electoral success. In recent decades many European countries have seen dramatic increases in the number of asylum applications. The general response has been to tighten borders against “illegal migrants”, shorten asylum procedures, limit the right of appeal, and pass responsibility to other nations—“safe third countries” through which the asylum seekers travelled en route to Western Europe. Switzerland is no exception to this trend. Despite Switzerland’s humanitarian tradition, the Swiss parliament, significantly influenced by right-wing populist parties, has recently approved a controversial new law on asylum seekers which is considered amongst the most restrictive in Europe.

The role played by state discourses in the portrayal of citizens and of those considered unsuitable for citizenship (Yuval-Davis, 1997) is currently of much scholarly interest. The concept of ‘discourse’ refers to groups of statements which structure the way something is thought about, and the way we act on the basis of that thinking. Discourse is powerful because it is productive. Discourses ‘naturalise’ and often implicitly universalize a particular view of the world and position subjects within it (Foucault, 1980; Gregory, 2002: 78). State discourses – conveyed by means of official documents, white papers, legislation, political rhetoric, and other documents, texts, and forms of representation (McDowell, 2003) - are particularly powerful discourses. Their dominance occurs not only because they are located in socially powerful institutions but also because they claim absolute truth (Foucault, 1980). For Van Dijk (2004: 15), the discourses of the political elites are particularly important, “because their legislative or policy-making positions place them in the crucible of discursive power and influence, namely there where discourse is not merely empty words, but has the direct force of law and regulation”. Studying state discourse is, for Van Dijk, an important means of understanding how prejudice, discrimination and racism are produced. He maintains that the socio-economic conditions of inequality of labour and

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colonial immigrants in Europe have been sustained and legitimized by state discourse.

Switzerland is a particularly interesting case for studying state discourses on foreigners. It has one of the largest percentages of foreigners in the world. At 21%, Switzerland has three times more foreigners than France, and twice as many as Germany, Austria, and the United States; however, the high percentage of foreigners is not the result of high absolute immigration but of citizenship laws based on the principle of blood-based descent (*jus sanguinis*) rather than on place of birth (*ius soli*) and of restrictive naturalisation practices. In fact, half of the 1.5 million ‘foreigners’ living in Switzerland (100’000 of them are refugees) were either born and raised in the country, or have lived there for more than fifteen years (Swiss Federal Statistics 2005: 19, 27). In 1998, with a rate of 1.4%, Switzerland had the lowest number of naturalisations in Europe after Germany. Switzerland’s reluctance to recognise itself as a country of immigration and to grant citizenship rights to immigrants is characteristic of countries with a ‘guest-worker’ tradition, such as Germany and Austria. In opposition to ‘classic’ immigration countries, such as the United States and Canada, where admission policies have been oriented to mass immigration with the intention of granting citizenship rights to the newcomers, guest-worker countries have imported temporary foreign labour without any intention of making them full members of society (Leitner, 1995). Excluding foreigners from citizenship has allowed Swiss populations to cultivate the feeling of having a unique identity (Tabin, 2004). Switzerland is also of special interest because, while it is true that it is a rare case of successful multi-ethnic nation building, it is also true that it has given rise to a segregated relationship between nationals and foreigners (Wimmer, 2002).

Recent studies of European immigration policies have argued that, despite steps towards the ‘Europeanisation’ of immigration policies, the national state continues to be the most influential entity in the determination of migrants’ rights (e.g. Kofman, 2002; Morris, 2001). Indeed, many studies have focused on the specific situation of individual states but have focused almost exclusively on countries belonging to the European Union (e.g., McDowell, 2003; Morris, 2001;

Schuster and Solomos, 1999; Sciortino, 2000; Staples, 1999; Thierry, 2000). So far, little attention has been given to European nations not belonging to the EU, such as Switzerland. Although much of the Swiss literature has focused on immigration and asylum policies, there has been little focus on studying policies as state discourse (Riaño and Wastl-Walter, 2006).

The aim of this paper is to address the literature gap by examining Swiss state discourses on asylum. The study is based on the perspective of critical discourse analysis, “an approach that specifically focuses on the role of discourse in the reproduction of power, dominance and inequality” (van Dijk, 2004: 20). The practical study of state discourse focuses on three dimensions of analysis: the discourse itself, the context of discourse, and the historical events surrounding the discourse. In the first dimension, the analysis of discourse consists of examining legal texts containing policies on refugees, complemented by official position papers and politicians’ speeches. In the second dimension, the context analysis is based on the idea that state discourses are not independent formulations but rather a result of competing and contradictory forces in society (Foucault, 1980). Such forces result from the diverse interests of groups and individuals acting in various arenas of society at the national and international levels: political (e.g. political parties, national governments, social movements), economic (e.g. industrial associations and industry representatives), and cultural (e.g. scientists and the media). The contextual analysis is based on the following question: What forces have been particularly successful in influencing the formulation of Swiss state discourses on refugees? The third dimension of the analysis, the historical perspective, is based on the idea that discourses are not static but vary over space and time (Blunt, 1999). Thus, the historical analysis examines shifts in policies and state discourses of refugees in Switzerland from the end of the 19th century up to today. The analysis is supported by a review of published material on the history of asylum policies (Arlettaz and Arlettaz, 2004; Arlettaz and Burkart, 1988; Efonayi et al., 2005; Jost, 1998 Kury, 2002; Piguet, 2004; Social Archive, 2003; Tanner, 1998).

2 Historical shifts in Swiss policies on asylum

State constructions of immigrants and policies on immigration and asylum have significantly changed in Switzerland from the country's first wave of immigration in the 19th Century up to today. The interaction of several forces and events seem to have influenced those shifts including most notably: the outbreak of the two world wars, the rise and fall of the communist regimes, the rapid increase in numbers of refugees during the 1990s; the globalisation of refugee flows and the recent weakening of the Swiss economy. Four main periods have been identified in this paper regarding the discursive construction of refugees: (a) before and during the First World War, a time when humanitarian values prevailed in Switzerland and refugees were seen by the government as worthy of asylum; (b) after the First World War and during the Second World War when Jewish refugees were conceived by the political elite as a cultural danger; (c) after the Second World War, when anti-communist feelings prevailed in the country and the government's policies towards refugees from those countries turned very liberal, and (d) from the 1990s to today, when the numbers of asylum-seekers significantly increased, populist right-wing parties constructed them as criminals, and the government's policies towards refugees became very restrictive.

2.2 Before and during the First World War: *Refugees as worthy of asylum*

Switzerland's has a long humanitarian tradition. It's tradition as a place of refuge dates back four hundred years. In the 16th century, thousands of French Protestants, persecuted for their religious beliefs, sought refuge in Swiss cities. Many of these people became members of Switzerland's cultural, political, and entrepreneurial elite. The Swiss universities founded in the late-19th century benefited from the arrival of German intellectuals, who fled home when the liberal revolution of 1848-1849 failed (Efionayi et al., 2005)

Industrialisation in Switzerland began around 1850. Up until then, Switzerland had been a poor nation with high numbers of people leaving the country mainly because of its scarce agricultural and mineral resources. Industrialisation introduced a need for foreign labour, both skilled and unskilled. At this point,

both civil society and the government perceived foreigners as indispensable for the country's economic development. The country's national identity was still in a process of consolidation. The humanitarian mission provided a moral foundation for the country's process of national integration. Humanitarianism being a national value, the country's official discourses of the sixteenth to nineteenth centuries characterised the right to asylum as a basic principle of Swiss politics (Arlettaz and Arlettaz, 2004). The liberal policies of immigration and asylum that prevailed at the time led to the acceptance of many foreign nationals into the country (Arlettaz and Burkart, 1988).

The creation of the Red Cross, an international agency concerned with the alleviation of human suffering, is exemplary of the humanitarian spirit that prevailed during that time. Its founder, the Swiss philanthropist Henri Dunant (1828–1910), horrified by the suffering he saw at the Battle of Solferino (Italy), proposed the formation of voluntary aid societies for the relief of war victims. In 1863 the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) was established and in the following year twelve governments signed the Geneva Convention. Its conventions have now been ratified by almost 150 nations. The ICRC's mandate is to protect and assist victims of war and internal violence. Today, the ICRC operates worldwide, helping the victims of war, acting as a neutral mediator in cases of conflict, and promoting knowledge and respect for humanitarian law. The International Red Cross was awarded Nobel Peace Prizes in 1917 and 1944 (Oxford Reference, 2000).

The liberal immigration policies that prevailed in the pre-war period resulted in a rapid increase in the foreign population. The high numbers of foreigners and the presence of new cultural groups produced negative reactions among Switzerland's conservative political and cultural elite. As historians have shown (Jost 1998, Tanner 1998, Mächler, 1998, Kury 2002), some politicians, writers and scientists started disseminating discourses about the 'threat of barbaric and uncivilised peoples coming from the South and from the East' and expressing the desire to be 'strong enough to impose our culture on them'. Foreigners started to be seen as dangerous and the notion of "Überfremdung" - a term coined in Switzerland which refers to the idea that excessive numbers of foreigners could

threaten Swiss identity- made its way into public discourse. Right-wing politicians used this discourse before and after the First World War to exacerbate nationalist feelings among the population. Curiously, Überfremdung was the result of an ideological construction and not of a demographic reality. The numbers of foreigners in Switzerland actually decreased during the war but politicians used statistical extrapolations, instead of actual census statistics, to make their case for Überfremdung. The ‘foreigner’ question became a national issue, and the debate revolved around Swiss identity being put in danger (Arlettaz and Burkart, 1988). The outbreak of the First World War in 1914 dramatically changed the positive conceptualisation of foreigners that had prevailed until the end of the 19th Century. The liberal spirit of pre-war immigration policies was abandoned; the civil rights of foreigners living in Switzerland were restricted, they were no longer entitled to permanent residence in the country, and from then on, the notion of foreigner, rather than that of immigrant, was to prevail.

Switzerland’s neutral position during the First World War attracted many refugees. Although the government’s asylum policies became more restrictive, asylum was refused to very few refugees. In line with Switzerland’s humanitarian tradition, 700’000 people were granted provisory asylum during the war period. Many prominent intellectuals were among those refugees such as the Russian revolutionary Lenin, the French writer Romain Rolland and the initiators of the “Dada” movement in Switzerland. In order to take care of war refugees, the Swiss government built internment camps for 26’000 people. Further, 26’000 war-victims or tuberculosis sufferers were cured in Swiss health resorts (Social Archive, 2003).

Figure 1: “Switzerland during the 1914-1916 World War”. A Swiss Army card portrayed the vision of Switzerland as heaven-protected country in the midst of European chaos. *Source: Social Archive, 2003*

2.3 After the First World War and during the Second World War: *Jewish refugees as a danger to the country*

As the Second World War broke out in 1939, a national ‘culture of threat’ developed which led to aggravating the existing negative view of foreigners. Protecting national identity became one of the pillars of immigration and asylum policies. In 1942, using the influential slogan that “the boat is full”, the former Federal Councillor Eduard von Steiger argued that Switzerland no longer had any capacity to take more refugees (although only 8’000 refugees were living in Switzerland at the time; i.e. 0.2% of the resident population). According to that ideology, Switzerland should shift from a refugee country to a ‘transit country’. Consequently, the Swiss Federal Government tried to reduce the country’s attractiveness for refugees by prohibiting their right to work and to carry out political activities (Independent Commission of Experts Switzerland – Second World War, 1999).

The group of refugees most affected by the “the boat is full” rhetoric were the Jews. At the time, the general attitude towards Jews among representatives of the police force and justice circles was negative. Many of them feared the country’s ‘Jewification’ (Social Archive 2003). The Swiss naturalization authority

classified Jews as “elements who are difficult to assimilate” (Kury 2002, Picard, 1994). In response to such negative perceptions, the Federal government closed its asylum door for Jewish refugees. This has been explained in detail by the Independent Commission of Experts Switzerland – Second World War (1999), a commission of historians appointed by the Swiss parliament to examine Swiss refugee policy during WW II. In 1938, Switzerland introduced a visa requirement to “non-Aryan” Germans. Swiss civil servants were urged by the Foreigner’s Police, between 1936 and 1940, to use a “J” stamp to administratively label foreign Jews. In the summer of 1942, when Nazi troops occupied the southern part of Vichy France, sending Jews scrambling for refuge, the Swiss government closed the country’s borders for refugees entering “solely on racial grounds”. According to Koller (1996), between 1940 and 1945 at least 24’000 Jews were sent back over the Swiss border and many of them found death in German concentration camps.

The government’s anti-humanitarian policy towards Jewish refugees was strongly criticized by many prominent Swiss intellectuals. Ordinary citizens, but also military personnel and ambassadors, tried in all manner of ways to protect Jewish refugees, against the will of the Swiss state. Protests from the public increased in the early 1940s and started having effect shortly thereafter. As Germany’s defeat became evident, the government started liberalising asylum policies. As an example, in the summer of 1944, the Federal government gave instructions not to send Jews over the border against their will. After World War II, the Swiss government recognized that Swiss authorities were responsible for denying admission to many Jewish refugees. The government stressed its willingness to uphold the humanitarian tradition of the country, and, in 1954, signed the Geneva Convention relating to the Status of Refugees of 1951 (Piguet, 2004).

At the same time that the Swiss government refused many Jewish refugees, an impressive number of other refugees found asylum in Switzerland during the Second World War. Whereas at the beginning of the war approximately 8’000 refugees lived in the country, in 1945, towards the end of the war, approximately

115'000 refugees had found asylum in Switzerland. A third of all the refugees were individuals from the armies of 38 countries. For example, 10'000 Polish soldiers who had fought alongside France were admitted for asylum in Switzerland. The refugees' labour was used in many cases for building roads and for agricultural activity (Social Archive, 2003).

2.3 After the Second World War into the 1980s: *Refugees from communist countries are welcome*

In the two decades following the Second World War, the Swiss government adopted a liberal policy of giving sanctuary to refugees from communist countries in Eastern Europe. In 1956 13'700 Hungarians were allowed to settle permanently after the uprising in 1956. In 1968, 13'000 Czechoslovakian nationals came to Switzerland. These people, who were often well-educated, had little difficulty in obtaining refugee status. The government and the public gave them a warm welcome, not surprising considering the strong anti-communist sentiments during that time period. The government embraced an open door policy towards Hungarians and Czechoslovakians. It established a maximum number of refugees that could be taken but individual applications were not necessary and there was no selection process. The Swiss Red-Cross organised the transport of refugees from Eastern Europe into Switzerland. Other non-communist countries around the world followed similar policies (Piguet, 2004).

Figure 2: “Help the Hungarians”. Picture of demonstrators in Zurich which illustrates the prevailing public support for refugees from communist countries (1956).
Source: Social Archive, 2003.

In 1963, Tibetan refugees came to Switzerland fleeing China's invasion of Tibet. Perceptions of Tibetans and of Tibetan culture were very positive in Switzerland and thus the government officially accepted a total of 1'000 Tibetans as refugees, most of who had come to the country with the support of the Swiss Red-Cross. In the mid-1970s, the arrival of a few hundred Chilean dissidents fleeing Pinochet's regime ignited controversial debates about the justification of their asylum. Swiss humanitarian groups, including churches and left-oriented organisations, lobbied for the acceptance of Chilean refugees. A total number of 1'600 were accepted. All these events spurred the creation of a new federal asylum policy in 1981, which codified the country's relatively generous practices. It defined the rules for the refugee status determination procedure and gave the Confederation the policymaking power, while clearly giving cantons the responsibility of implementing policy (Piguet, 2004).

After 1981, two trends emerged regarding asylum-seeking. First, the number of applications, which had been steady at about 1'000 per year during the 1970s, increased exponentially (see Table 1). Secondly, most of the refugees — except for a large number of Polish refugees in 1982 — came from non-European countries: Turkey, Zaire, Sri Lanka, Cambodia, Vietnam, Laos, and from the Middle East. Unlike the anti-communist dissidents, they were not always professionals or university-educated. Some came from rural areas, some had not even finished primary school, while others had university degrees that were not recognized in Europe. In addition, a weak economy made it hard for these non-European refugees to find work. With more people from outside Europe filing applications, asylum became a sensitive subject in the mid-1980s. In public debates, refugees were called “asylum seekers” to indicate that they did not deserve refugee status (Piguet, 2004). Public reactions to Tamil refugees who had come to Switzerland fleeing civil war in Sri Lanka were very negative. The Swiss popular press stigmatised them as ‚Leather Jacket Tamils’ and as prototypes of criminal refugees (Social Archive, 2003). In 1987, 1986 and 1990, as a response to rising negative feelings against asylum-seekers, the government carried out progressive revisions to the liberal 1981 law in order to make it more

restrictive. Consequently, only a decreasing percentage of asylum requests were accepted, even from people fleeing civil wars and violence (Efionayi et al., 2005). As a rough indicator for this trend, positive answers to applications averaged 92.2% between 1975 and 1979. That number dropped to an average of 55.8% between 1980 and 1984, then to an average of 8.7% between 1985 and 1989 (Swiss Federal Office for Migration, 2006b).

Table 1: Evolution in the numbers of asylum requests and asylum approvals 1964-2005. *Source:* Swiss Federal Office for Migration 2006b.

Note: The numbers of asylum approvals in 1969 are higher than numbers of asylum requests because of the Swiss government’s resolution to accept a total number of 13’000 Czechoslovakian refugees without them having to hand in an individual request.

2.4 As of the 1990s: *Asylum-seekers as “criminals and drug dealers”*

As the civil war broke out in the former Yugoslavia, the numbers of asylum seekers to Switzerland significantly increased. In 1991, demands for asylum reached a high point with 41’629 requests (see Table 1). Between 1990 and 2002, Switzerland received a total of 146’587 asylum applications from the war-torn Balkans. About 10’000 people were granted asylum, and 62’000 received temporary or subsidiary protection over the course of several years (Swiss Federal Office for Migration, 2006a). Most of the asylum seekers from Bosnia and Kosovo had to leave Switzerland after conflicts ended in 1995 and 1999, respectively. Those who returned home, including those who waited several

years to do so, benefited from a Swiss government return program consisting of financial support, construction materials, and support for their home communities (Swiss Federal Audit Office, 2003).

The Swiss public became concerned about the increasing number of asylum applications, especially because the economy was in recession and unemployment was rising. Visibly different and forcibly idle for long periods, asylum seekers became an easy target of public resentment. The government had no coherent answer to the problem of rising numbers of asylum seekers (Parini, 1997). As a response, a completely revised asylum law came into force in 1999. Among many other changes, the law was made more restrictive and introduced new grounds for non-admission to a regular asylum procedure.

Despite the fact that the number of accepted refugees declined during the 1990s (see Table 1), in 2002 the nationalist Swiss People's Party (SVP) launched a referendum against the “Abuse of Asylum Rights”. The referendum's intent was to introduce further restrictions on asylum law consequently reducing Switzerland's attractiveness for asylum seekers. A narrow majority of 50.1% of the Swiss population voted against the tightening of asylum law. Anti-immigrant sentiments helped the nationalist Swiss People's Party (SVP), which depicted asylum seekers as “criminals and drug dealers” win the biggest share of the parliamentary votes in the 2003 general elections. Following the elections, the head of the Swiss People's Party, Christoph Blocher, became Minister of Justice and Police and assumed responsibility for migration and asylum policy.

In December 2005, the Swiss Parliament accepted the tightening of the country's legislation on asylum. The Minister of Justice Christoph Blocher masterminded and pushed the tightening of the asylum law. The measures were designed to crack down on rejected asylum seekers and to reduce costs in the asylum administration. According to the new law, asylum applicants without identity papers would have to prove that it was impossible for them to obtain such papers. Rejected asylum seekers would have their social welfare payments stopped. The aim was to speed up their deportation. Under the new law, the maximum

detention period for foreigners awaiting deportation would also increase to 18 months for adults and nine months for minors over 15. The humanitarian principle of complementary protection status for individuals who do not qualify for refugee status but who are still in need and equally deserving of international protection (for example, because they could be exposed to serious harm in the context of an ongoing conflict) was removed (Migration und Bevölkerung, 2005).

The government's tightening of asylum law came at a time when the number of asylum applications in Switzerland had been falling steadily. In 2004 there were 14'248 asylum applications in Switzerland. This was 32% lower than the previous year. In 2005, there were 10'061 applications, the lowest number since 1986. This is again 29% lower compared to 2004 (see Figure 1). The largest single group of applicants came from Serbia and Montenegro (1'506) followed by Turkey, Somalia, Iraq and Bulgaria (Swiss Federal Office for Migration, 2006a). The reduction in the number of applications for asylum is a trend common to other European countries such as Germany, Netherlands and the United Kingdom (Migration und Bevölkerung, 2005). The Swiss Federal Migration Office attributed the decline to the implementation of tougher immigration policies over the past few years in Switzerland. According to Newland (2005), the widespread coincidence of lower numbers and increasing restrictions reflects a complex supply and demand dynamic. The lower demand for asylum is a result of the calming of major refugee-producing conflicts in places like the Balkans, Afghanistan and Iraq; the number of asylum seekers moving from the latter two countries to the industrialized world fell by more than 80 percent in the past three years. Asylum seekers have also been discouraged by the restrictive measures adopted by European countries including stricter controls at the EU's external borders.

The United Nations High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR) has expressed serious concerns about the tightening of asylum law in Switzerland. The commission has been particularly concerned by provisions restricting access to asylum for people with no valid travel or identity documents. The 1951

Convention specifically acknowledges and provides for refugees who may have had to flee their country without being able to obtain valid travel or identity documents. According to the UNHCR, the new provision could make access to asylum procedures exceedingly difficult for genuine refugees. The planned measures make Swiss law among the most severe in Europe. The UNHCR also regretted that the humanitarian principle of complementary protection status was not retained. This would have brought Swiss legislation closer to European norms (UNHCR, 2005b). A ‘Coalition for a humanitarian Switzerland’, made up by the centre-left Social Democrats, the Green Party, churches, humanitarian organisations and trade unions, has already announced referendums against both the new asylum legislation and the proposed foreigners’ law. They believe the new asylum law breaches the 1951 Geneva refugee convention and violates international law.

Figure 3: Macedonian asylum seekers under threat of deportation are given refuge by a Lausanne church, 2005. *Picture:* Julie Hunt/Swissinfo

Switzerland’s history of policies and official discourses on refugees reveals two opposing trends. On the one hand, during the industrial expansion in the period up to the First World War both civil society and the government perceived foreigners as indispensable for the country’s economic development. The positive conceptualisation of foreigners led to an open immigration and asylum policy whereby the country provided refuge to many asylum- seekers. On the other hand, after the First World War, a national ‘culture of threat’ developed and Jewish refugees were represented as a cultural danger; a representation that served the purpose of legitimising their exclusion from the right to asylum. During the post-war period of economic expansion, the Swiss government once

again adopted a liberal refugee policy of giving sanctuary to refugees from communist countries in Eastern Europe, most of whom were well educated. In response to the Swiss public’s increasing negativity towards refugees asylum policies since the 1980s have become more restrictive. The public’s negative feelings were associated with the exponential increase in the number of applications, the origin of refugees from countries outside of Europe, refugee claimant’s basic education and the progressive weakening of the economy. This trend has continued into the 1990s where the populist Swiss People’s Party have constructed refugees as criminals and drug dealers. Table 2 below summarises the variety of conceptualisations of refugees in Swiss asylum policies.

Table 2: Conceptualisations of foreigners in Swiss asylum policies (1850-2005)

Period	Asylum Policies	Discourse
Before the First World War	Liberal policies of asylum	<i>Refugees as worthy of asylum</i>
After the First World War and during the Second World War	Tightening of asylum policies	<i>Jewish refugees as a danger for the country</i>
Post World War II into the 1980s	Relatively liberal asylum policies	<i>Refugees from communist states as welcome for asylum</i>
1990s onwards	Tightening of asylum law	<i>Asylum seekers as criminals and drug dealers</i>

3 Conclusions

This paper has studied the history of the discursive construction of refugees by Swiss asylum policies since 1850 until today. State representations of refugees have shifted from a predominantly humanitarian attitude towards asylum-seekers before the First World War to a mainly defensive attitude, which partly persists today, where asylum-seekers are increasingly perceived as a cultural threat and a financial burden. Several events have influenced these shifts in discourse: the outbreak of the two world wars, the rise and fall of the communist regimes, the rapid increase in numbers of refugees during the 1990s; the globalisation of refugee flows, the recent weakening of the Swiss economy and the rise of populist right-wing parties. Several actors have influenced the formulation of refugee policies including xenophobic groups and right-wing parties on the one hand, and progressive intellectuals and humanitarian organisations on the other.

Right wing parties have played a significant role in the recent tightening of asylum law, considered amongst the most restrictive in Europe (UNHCR, 2005b). As in many other industrialized countries, the recent rise of the populist right-wing Swiss People’s Party, which has engaged in xenophobic rhetoric generally characterizing asylum seekers as criminals and cheats, has strengthened and legitimised a discourse which emphasizes the costs and inefficiencies of the asylum administration system. More important than the direct power of these parties has been the pressure that more centrist parties have felt to co-opt the right-wing agenda by adopting restrictive measures themselves.

Imaginations of race, class and political systems have structured Swiss state discourses on refugees. Racialisation, the practice of distinguishing certain groups from others through the attribution of negatively evaluated features in order to justify their exclusion from equal access to social and political resources (Kofman, 2004) has been present in refugee policies for a long time. For example, the racialised representation of Jewish refugees as a cultural threat for the country has had the function of legitimising their exclusion from the right to asylum seeking. A positive representation of Tibetan culture has, on the contrary, led to willing policies of acceptance towards Tibetan refugees. At the same time, the unrestricted acceptance of educated refugees from Eastern Europe has introduced a differentiation of refugees according to class. Less educated refugees from countries outside Europe have been constructed as criminals and their acceptance for asylum has been much more reluctant. Imaginations of political systems have also influenced the government’s refugee policies. The negative representations of the communist system that prevailed in the 1960s led the Swiss government to an unquestioned acceptance of refugees from Eastern Europe.

Switzerland is only the most recent example of new restrictions on the ability to seek asylum in industrialized countries. Asylum practices in Europe in the recent past have put asylum seekers through lengthy and costly procedures while excluding them from the labour market and giving them fairly generous public benefits, making it easy to portray them as a burden. Denmark has abandoned the

concept of a humanitarian status for people fleeing from war and violent chaos, and will only consider asylum claims on the basis of a narrow and highly individualized interpretation of the Refugee Convention. The United States and Australia continue to intercept would-be asylum seekers at sea, and make it almost impossible for them to be accepted as refugees (although the United States makes some exceptions for intercepted Cubans) in the country they were trying to access. Italy has also turned to interception at sea, and has on at least two occasions deported hundreds of people without allowing UNHCR to confirm that they had been adequately screened for refugee claims. During the EU summit in 2003, the United Kingdom proposed that asylum seekers have their claims processed in transit centres outside the EU, and that refugee protection be provided in designated zones close to their regions of origin. In the meantime, domestic legislation in the UK proceeded to increase the capacity for detention of asylum seekers, provided for electronic monitoring, stiffened requirements for documentation, and added new criteria for calling an asylum applicant's credibility into question (Newland, 2005).

Ideally, immigration and asylum policies should allow governments to respond to the country's long-term economic and demographic needs for high- and low-skilled workers and to take account of international conventions on human rights. But given the political sensitivity of immigration, the influence of the Swiss People's Party, and the power of the Swiss people to vote on migration policy via referendums, Switzerland looks likely to maintain its emphasis on control and costs. Indeed, parliamentary discussions about revising the Aliens Law from 1931 and the Asylum Law from 1999 lead to new laws focused on these criteria rather than on demographics, economics or human rights. The future of Switzerland's asylum policy lies in the hands of the Swiss voters: the referendum against the new asylum legislation which has been launched by the 'Coalition for a humanitarian Switzerland', shall decide the path that Switzerland is to follow regarding asylum rights.

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